

Academic Procrastination and Burnout among Grade 11 Students

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ABSTRACT: This study aimed to determine the significant relationship between academic procrastination and burnout. Simple random sampling was used, and it included 53 students. Through non-experimental quantitative descriptive-correlational research technique, validated questionnaire, Mean, Pearson-Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson-r), and Simple Linear Regression, results showed that the level of academic procrastination was moderate or sometimes manifested. It was also found that the level of student burnout was moderate or sometimes manifested. There was a significant relationship between academic procrastination and burnout. This means that students who frequently put things off are more likely to experience feelings of exhaustion, cynicism, and a sense of inadequacy related to their studies. Accordingly, academic procrastination significantly influences student's burnout. School officials were recommended to implement a multi-tiered policy to address student procrastination and burnout.

KEY WORDS: Academic procrastination, Burnout, Grade 11 students, Descriptive-correlational study

INTRODUCTION

The later years of high school are a period of intense academic pressure. Students navigate standardized testing anxieties, college application deadlines, and a rapidly increasing workload, creating a breeding ground for burnout. Burnout, characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization (cynicism towards studies), and reduced academic self-efficacy (feeling like ineffective learning) (Maslach et al., 2001), is not just a workplace phenomenon. Researchers suggest a significant negative impact on students' academic well-being, leading to decreased motivation, engagement, and even dropout rates (Olson et al., 2023; Ruy et al., 2023; Abreu Alves et al., 2022; Norez, 2017).

Understanding student burnout is crucial for several reasons. Burnout expands the concept beyond the traditional work context, enriching our understanding. Studies reveal a concerning prevalence of burnout among students globally (Zhou et al., 2024; Ghimire et al., 2022; Rosales-Ricardo & Ferreira, 2022). Investigating burnout in eleventh-grade students allows the researchers to identify students at a critical juncture, potentially mitigating long-term academic consequences.

The complex association between academic procrastination and burnout further accentuates the importance of this research. Students experiencing burnout may resort to procrastination as a coping mechanism to temporarily escape overwhelming demands (Jochmann et al., 2024; Xu & Ba, 2022). However, procrastination can exacerbate burnout by creating last-minute stress and a sense of urgency, ultimately hindering academic performance (Logenio et al., 2023; Madigan & Curran, 2021; Xu, 2021). Numerous studies support this association. For instance, Lacson et al. (2023) found a significant and positive association between academic procrastination and burnout. Similarly, Hosseinpour Kharrazi and Ghanizadeh (2023) demonstrated that procrastination significantly predicts student burnout.

This study was anchored in the Self-Control Theory, which posits that individuals rely on self-control resources to regulate their behavior and achieve goals (Heatherton & Wagner, 2011; Kirschenbaum, 1997; Baumeister & Heatherton, 1996). Procrastination depletes these resources, leaving students emotionally drained and vulnerable to burnout. Additionally, the Cyclical Model of Academic Procrastination (Steel, 2007) suggests that procrastination creates a cycle of emotions (anxiety, guilt) that further fuels procrastination and contributes to burnout. The Job Demands – Resources Model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007) offers another perspective. Academic demands act as stressors, while effective time management skills serve as resources. Procrastination weakens these resources, amplifying the impact of academic demands and leading to burnout.

This study consists of the independent variable (academic procrastination) and the dependent variable (burnout). Academic procrastination is an intentional delay or postponement of necessary academic tasks despite awareness of potential negative consequences. This behavior is characterized by a combination of behavioral and emotional aspects, including voluntary delay, intended but unimplemented actions, and accompanying feelings of discomfort (Araya-Castillo, 2023; González-Brignardello et al., 2023; Kurniadin et al., 2023; Bobe et al., 2022). On the other hand, burnout refers to emotional exhaustion, cynicism, and

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inefficiency, emphasizing personal and workplace factors contributing to it (Maslach & Leiter, 2016). In this study, students' burnout was measured in terms of exhaustion of school work, cynicism toward the meaning of school, and sense of inadequacy at school. Defining each term, *exhaustion from school work* is a feeling of being emotionally and physically drained by academic demands. In contrast, *cynicism toward the meaning of school* reflects a negative, detached attitude towards academics. *A sense of inadequacy at school* encompasses a feeling of ineffectiveness and a lack of belief in one's ability to succeed academically (Salmela-Aro et al., 2009).

This study delves deeper into the context of Grade 11 private college students in the Island Garden City of Samal. While existing research provides a comprehensive understanding of burnout and its association with procrastination, limited studies explore its nuances within this location. Filling this gap is crucial for developing targeted interventions and promoting student well-being. Thus, this study aimed to address the following objectives: (1) to determine the level of academic procrastination among Grade 11 students, (2) to determine the level of burnout among Grade 11 students, (3) to determine the significant relationship between academic procrastination and burnout, and (4) to determine the significant influence of academic procrastination to student's burnout.

The significance of the study extends beyond the academic realm. Globally, it contributes to the existing body of knowledge on student burnout, enriching the understanding of its impact and potential interventions. Locally, the findings will benefit the school officials, teachers, parents, and future researchers by informing strategies to support Grade 11 students and foster a more positive learning environment. They can utilize these insights to develop effective strategies for mitigating burnout.

METHODOLOGY

Research Respondents

The study's respondents were the fifty-three (53) senior high school students from the Humanities and Social Sciences and Accounting, Business and Management strands officially enrolled in the UM Peñaplata College Senior High School Department school year 2022-2023 chosen through a simple random sampling technique. A simple random sampling technique is a type of sampling technique that uses random selection to choose study participants from a larger population. If a random sample is taken, all population members have an equal and independent chance of being chosen. This technique is often used when there is no efficient way to manually select a sample. With simple random sampling, each student in the population has an equal chance of being selected to represent the sample. Students cannot be excluded from the sample based on their background or qualities. This enables the researcher to get an accurate picture of the population. Simple random sampling also eliminates bias in the selection process (Noor et al., 2022). In addition, several researchers suggest that if parametric tests are to be employed, 30 – 500 subjects would be the necessary sample size (Bacala et al., 2024; Morales et al., 2024; Ross, 2020; Delice, 2010; Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2006; Baykul, 1999).

Research Instruments

Two sets of questionnaires were adapted from authors of different studies, which experts in questionnaire construction validated. The adapted standardized questionnaire is valid in contents as it underwent a series of modifications to classify the most reliable and valid questions. Further, the authors have already tested and proven it. The questionnaire was designed in a very comprehensive form with the help of expert validators to provide the respondents with ease and comfort in answering each question and understanding the study's objective.

The first part of the questionnaire contained five statements for academic procrastination adapted from the study of Balkis and Duru (2022). The degree of academic procrastination was rated on a five-point Likert-type scale, which was rated as follows: 5 – Very high, 4 - High, 3 - Moderate, 2 – Low, and 1 = Very low.

The second set of instrument used measures the extent of student burnout. The questionnaire was adapted from the study of Salmela-Aro et al. (2009). There were three subscales: exhaustion at schoolwork, cynicism toward the meaning of school, and a sense of inadequacy at school. On this variable, each indicator is composed of the following items: Exhaustion at Schoolwork (4 items), Cynicism toward the meaning of school (3 items), and Sense of inadequacy at school (2 items), with a total of 9 items. This 9-item survey used a 5-point Likert-type Scale (from Very Low to Very High).

Design and Procedure

This research used a non-experimental quantitative descriptive correlation design. A correlational study is a research design examining the relationship between two or more variables. Correlational studies are non-experimental, meaning the researcher does not manipulate or control any variables (Bhandari, 2023; Cherry, 2023; Monteroso et al., 2023). It intends to determine the association between academic procrastination and burnout among Grade 11 students.

The researcher sought approval from the Dean of the College; after the approval, the letter was sent to the Senior High School principal before administrating the research instruments. Consent was also sought from the respondents for voluntary participation. Respondents were given ample time to complete the tool. The instrument was retrieved immediately after the

respondents had answered the tool entirely. After gathering the necessary data, these were tabulated, subjected to statistical treatment, and interpreted accordingly.

Statistical Tools

Mean – This was used to determine the academic procrastination and burnout level among Grade 11 students.

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient – This was used to determine the significant relationship between academic procrastination and burnout.

Simple Linear Regression – This was used to determine the significant influence of academic procrastination on student burnout.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Academic Procrastination

Presented in Table 1 is the level of academic procrastination among Grade 11 students. Among the five (5) statements about academic procrastination, the statement “*I get distracted by other, more fun things when I am supposed to work on schoolwork*” got the highest mean ($M=3.77$, $SD=.93$), which was described as high or always manifested. This means that distractions from more enjoyable activities significantly contribute to academic procrastination among students. This suggests that students often procrastinate by choosing leisure activities over academic responsibilities, adversely impacting their academic performance and overall productivity. This was supported by Wiwatowska et al. (2023), highlighting that high procrastinators are less attentive to task-relevant stimuli due to increased susceptibility to distractions such as mind wandering and engaging in more enjoyable activities. Procrastination is often accompanied by a preference for non-urgent, enjoyable tasks over urgent, necessary ones, leading to decreased academic performance and increased anxiety (Saplavska & Jerkunkova, 2018).

However, the statement “*I know I should work on schoolwork, but I just don't do it,*” got the lowest mean ($M=2.94$, $SD=1.18$) described as moderate or sometimes manifested, suggests that the behavior it represents is not consistently present but occurs with noticeable frequency. This indicates a pattern of procrastination or motivational issues that, while not pervasive, are not significant enough to impact academic performance. Procrastination is often linked to psychological factors, including lack of motivation, fear of failure, and poor time management skills. For instance, Steel (2007) highlighted that procrastination is a common self-regulatory failure, where individuals delay tasks despite knowing it may lead to adverse outcomes. This aligns with Tuckman’s Procrastination Scale (Tuckman, 1991), which identifies procrastination and its potential link to negative consequences. Moreover, Ferrari et al. (1995) found that procrastination may be linked to motivational factors and difficulties with task prioritization.

Lastly, the overall academic procrastination level of the students ($M=3.19$, $SD=.85$) was described as moderate or sometimes manifested, suggesting that while several students exhibit procrastination behaviors, there are also students who do not procrastinate regularly or at all. This means that some students often struggle with motivation and self-regulation, while others possess certain traits and employ strategies that help them manage their time and tasks more effectively. Various studies suggested that procrastination is associated with a lack of self-efficacy and poor goal-setting behaviors (Wang et al., 2021; Ramzi & Saed, 2019; Klassen et al., 2008). Researchers, including Haycock et al. (2008), suggest that students with low self-efficacy and high anxiety are prone to procrastination (van Eerde & Klingsieck, 2018; Klassen et al., 2008). Conversely, Zimmerman's model of self-regulated learning emphasizes the importance of setting clear goals and monitoring progress to achieve academic success (Zimmerman, 2012). This aligns with van Eerde & Klingsieck's (2018) research, which suggests that procrastination stems from self-regulation issues, including ineffective goal-setting." Moreover, Pintrich and De Groot (1990) found that students with higher intrinsic motivation and self-regulation are more engaged and perform better academically, as they can manage their time and prioritize tasks effectively.

Table 1. Level of Academic Procrastination

Statements	SD	M	Descriptive Level
1. I put off projects until the last minute.	.95	3.30	Moderate
2. I know I should work on schoolwork, but I just don't do it.	1.18	2.94	Moderate
3. I get distracted by other, more fun things when I am supposed to work on schoolwork.	.93	3.77	High
4. When given an assignment, I usually out it way and forget about it until it is almost due.	1.23	2.98	Moderate
5. I frequently find myself putting important deadlines off.	1.09	2.96	Moderate
Overall Mean	.85	3.19	Moderate

Note: N = 53, M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation

Level of Burnout

Presented in Table 2 is the level of burnout among Grade 11 students. Data revealed that exhaustion at schoolwork (M=3.47, SD=.67) was described as high or oftentimes manifested. The high exhaustion at schoolwork mean score depicts a concerning picture of student well-being. This result aligns with research on academic strain, where heavy workloads, deadlines, and pressure can lead to significant exhaustion (Schaufeli et al., 2009). This exhaustion is a key indicator of potential burnout, a condition characterized by emotional and physical depletion (Maslach & Leiter, 2016, 2009). Studies have shown that exhaustion often precedes cynicism and feelings of inadequacy in the burnout process (Lee et al., 2020; Maslach & Leiter, 2016; Maslach et al., 2001).

Table 2. Level of Burnout

Indicators	SD	M	Descriptive Level
Exhaustion at Schoolwork	.67	3.47	High
Cynicism Toward the Meaning of School	.94	3.27	Moderate
Sense of Inadequacy at School	.86	3.32	Moderate
Overall Mean	.72	3.35	Moderate

Note: N = 53, M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation

However, cynicism toward the meaning of school (M=3.27, SD=.94) and a sense of inadequacy at school (M=3.32, SD=.86) were described as moderate or sometimes manifested. The results suggest that students have yet to reach a critical burnout stage. Various studies (Özhan & Yüksel, 2021; Salmera-Aro et al., 2009) highlight the importance of intervening before cynicism and inadequacy become severe. Early intervention can prevent a downward spiral towards complete disengagement from school. Lastly, the overall burnout level (M=3.35, SD=0.72) among students was described as moderate or sometimes manifested, indicating that a notable portion of this group struggles with exhaustion, cynicism, and a sense of inadequacy related to school, though likely not a constant or debilitating level. This implies a widespread issue, but one where interventions can significantly impact. Studies like Basith et al. (2023) and Sari et al. (2020) identified moderate levels of academic burnout among students.

Significance of the Relationship between Academic Procrastination and Burnout

As shown in Table 3, the significance of the relationship between academic procrastination and burnout among students is shown. Results revealed an overall r-value of .614 with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 degree of a significant relationship. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. It can be seen that academic procrastination; has a significant relationship to the domains of burnout. This means that students who frequently put things off are more likely to experience feelings of exhaustion, cynicism, and a sense of inadequacy related to their studies. The stress of constantly playing catch-up can be draining, which can make it even harder to focus and get started on tasks, creating a cycle of delay.

It was found in the study of Balkis (2013) that academic procrastination was positively correlated to all domains of burnout. Similar studies (Lacson et al., 2023; Maloloy-on et al., 2023; Purnomo et al., 2020) have also found a relationship between procrastination and student burnout. Students who procrastinate are less likely to finish tasks promptly, take significantly longer to complete academic assignments, often delay starting their exam preparation, and generally study for shorter periods (Balkis, 2013; Hurley, 2003; Jackson et al., 2003; Lay & Burns, 1991; Lay, 1986). These collective findings imply that awareness and intervention are crucial. Educators, counselors, and students should recognize the impact of procrastination on burnout. Addressing procrastination not only improves academic performance but also contributes to overall well-being. Effective stress management strategies and balancing priorities can help prevent burnout.

Table 3. Significance of the Relationship between Academic Procrastination and Burnout

Academic Procrastination	Burnout			
	Exhaustion at Schoolwork	Cynicism Toward the Meaning of School	Sense of Inadequacy at School	Overall
Overall	.531* (.000)	.677* (.000)	.381* (.005)	.614* (.000)

*p<.05 – Significant

Regression Analysis of the Influence of Academic Procrastination on Burnout

Presented in Table 4 is the regression analysis of the influence of academic procrastination on burnout. The data in Table 4 shows a significant influence of academic procrastination on burnout. The obtained F-value of 30.811 is significant at p<0.05, which indicates a model fit. Also, the R-squared value of .377 suggested that burnout's variance (F) was attributed to the student's

academic procrastination. This means that .623, or 62.3% of the variance, could be credited to other things that are already beyond the concern of this study.

The significant influence of academic procrastination on burnout suggests that students who frequently delay their academic tasks are more prone to experiencing burnout. This association implies that procrastination can exacerbate stress levels, reduce academic performance, and ultimately lead to emotional and physical exhaustion. For instance, Kim and Park (2023) indicated that procrastination directly impacts burnout and amplifies other stress-inducing behaviors. Similarly, Qu et al. (2022) demonstrated that academic procrastination contributed to student burnout, with negative emotions mediating. Hosseinpour Kharrazi and Ghanizadeh (2023) also demonstrated that procrastination significantly predicts student burnout.

Table 4. Regression Analysis of the Influence of Academic Procrastination on Burnout

Variable	Burnout		
	B	t	Sig.
Constant	1.706	5.557	<.001
Academic Procrastination	.516	5.551	<.001*
<i>R</i>	.614		
<i>R</i> ²	.377		
<i>F</i>	30.811		
<i>p</i>	<.000*		

**p*<.05 – Significant

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were derived:

1. The academic procrastination level of the students was moderate or sometimes manifested, suggesting that while several students exhibit procrastination behaviors; there are also students who do not procrastinate regularly or at all. This means that some students often struggle with motivation and self-regulation, while others possess certain traits and employ strategies that help them manage their time and tasks more effectively.
2. The student's burnout level was described as moderate or sometimes manifested; indicating that a notable portion of this group struggles with exhaustion, cynicism, and a sense of inadequacy related to school, though likely not a constant or debilitating level. This implies a widespread issue, but one where interventions can significantly impact.
3. There was a significant relationship between academic procrastination and burnout. This means that students who frequently put things off are more likely to experience feelings of exhaustion, cynicism, and a sense of inadequacy related to their studies. The stress of constantly playing catch-up can be draining, which can make it even harder to focus and get started on tasks, creating a cycle of delay.
4. Academic procrastination significantly influences student's burnout. This suggests that students who frequently delay their academic tasks are more prone to experiencing burnout. This association implies that procrastination can exacerbate stress levels, reduce academic performance, and ultimately lead to emotional and physical exhaustion.

Recommendations

After a careful review of the conclusions, the following recommendations were offered:

1. The school officials are recommended to implement a multi-tiered policy to address student procrastination and burnout. This policy would involve training teachers in time management and offering flexible deadlines. Additionally, student support services like academic advisors and counselors are readily available. Collaboration between teachers and parents through workshops would equip parents to recognize and support students struggling with procrastination at home. Finally, promoting student well-being through stress management and healthy lifestyle initiatives would create a more resilient student body.
2. Teachers are recommended to equip students with time management and self-regulation skills while offering flexible deadlines and creating engaging learning experiences. Teachers should identify students who are struggling for targeted support.
3. Parents are recommended to foster open communication about schoolwork, set a good example with their time management, and provide a supportive environment. Parents should help children develop healthy coping mechanisms for stress and maintain communication with teachers to stay informed and collaborate to address any concerns.
4. Students are recommended to set realistic goals, utilize time management tools, and reward themselves for completing tasks to maintain motivation.

5. Future researchers are recommended to test interventions to reduce procrastination and burnout, investigate the underlying reasons behind procrastination, conduct long-term studies to understand the lasting effects of procrastination on students, and explore the potential influence of technology on students' academic procrastination and burnout.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The overall success and completion of this research will be impossible without the Divine Guidance of our Almighty God. The authors also wish to thank UM Peñaplata College Research and Publication Center for the continued support of this research endeavor.

REFERENCES

1. Abreu Alves, S., Sinval, J., Lucas Neto, L., Marôco, J., Gonçalves Ferreira, A., & Oliveira, P. (2022). Burnout and dropout intention in medical students: the protective role of academic engagement. *BMC Medical Education*, 22(1), 83.
2. Araya-Castillo, L., Burgos, M., González, P., Rivera, Y., Barrientos, N., Yáñez Jara, V., ... & Sáez, W. (2023). Procrastination in university students: A proposal of a theoretical model. *Behavioral Sciences*, 13(2), 128.
3. Bacala, S. A., Abordaje, J. L., Labrador, L. M., Bacatan, R. J., & Bacatan, J. (2024). The Influence of Service Quality on Customer Engagement in Kaputian Beach Park. *Cognizance Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 4(1), 332-338.
4. Balkis, M. (2013). The relationship between academic procrastination and students' burnout. *Hacettepe Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 28(28-1).
5. Balkis, M., & Duru, E. (2022). The examining psychometric characteristics of Academic Procrastination Scale-Short Form. *Pamukkale Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi-Pamukkale University Journal Of Education*.
6. Bakker, A. B., & Demerouti, E. (2007). The job demands-resources model: State of the art. *Journal of managerial psychology*, 22(3), 309-328.
7. Basith, A., Rahman, M. S., & Moseki, U. R. (2023). Academic Burnout in Vocational High School Students. *International Journal of Multi Discipline Science (IJ-MDS)*, 6(1), 10-17.
8. Baumeister, R. F., & Heatherton, T. F. (1996). Self-regulation failure: An overview. *Psychological inquiry*, 7(1), 1-15.
9. Baykul, Y. (1999). *İstatistik: Metodlar ve uygulamalar*. Anı Yayıncılık.
10. Bhandari, P. (2023, June 22). *Correlational Research | When & How to Use*. Scribbr. Retrieved May 14, 2024, from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/correlational-research/>
11. Bobe, J., Schnettler, T., Scheunemann, A., Fries, S., Bäumle, L., Thies, D. O., ... & Grunschel, C. (2022). Delaying academic tasks and feeling bad about it: Development and validation of a six-item scale measuring academic procrastination. *European Journal of Psychological Assessment*.
12. Cherry, K. (2023, May 4). *Correlation studies in psychology research*. Verywell Mind. <https://www.verywellmind.com/correlational-research-2795774>
13. Delice, A. (2010). The Sampling Issues in Quantitative Research. *Educational Sciences: Theory and Practice*, 10(4), 2001-2018.
14. Ghimire, A., Adhikari, K., Subba, R., Sharma, B., Nepal, S., & Thapa, T. (2022). Academic Burnout among Students Studying in Selected Secondary School of Chitwan. *MedS Alliance Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences*, 2(3), 28-32.
15. González-Brignardello, M. P., Sánchez-Elvira Paniagua, A., & López-González, M. Á. (2023). Academic procrastination in children and adolescents: A Scoping review. *Children*, 10(6), 1016.
16. Haycock, L. A., McCarthy, P., & Skay, C. L. (1998). Procrastination in college students: The role of self-efficacy and anxiety. *Journal of counseling & development*, 76(3), 317-324.
17. Heatherton, T. F., & Wagner, D. D. (2011). Cognitive neuroscience of self-regulation failure. *Trends in cognitive sciences*, 15(3), 132-139.
18. Hosseinpour Kharrazi, F., & Ghanizadeh, A. (2023). The interplay among EFL learners' academic procrastination, learning approach, burnout, and language achievement. *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, 1-10.
19. Hurley, K. (2003). Trait procrastination, time management, and academic behaviour. *Journal of Social Behaviour and Personality*, 8(6), 47-66.
20. Jackson, T., Weiss, K. E., Lundquist, J. J., & Hooper, D. (2003). The Impact Of Hope, Procrastination, And Social Activity On Academic Performance Of Midwestern College Students. *Education*, 124(2).
21. Jochmann, A., Gusy, B., Lesener, T., & Wolter, C. (2024). Procrastination, depression and anxiety symptoms in university students: a three-wave longitudinal study on the mediating role of perceived stress. *BMC psychology*, 12(1), 276.

22. Kim, Y., & Park, K. (2023). The Relationship between Smartphone Addiction Tendencies and Academic Burnout in (under)Graduate Student: The Mediating Effects of Sleep Quality and Academic Procrastination. *Korean Association For Learner-Centered Curriculum And Instruction*.
23. Kirschenbaum, D. S. (1987). Self-regulatory failure: A review with clinical implications. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 7(1), 77-104.
24. Klassen, R. M., Krawchuk, L. L., & Rajani, S. (2008). Academic procrastination of undergraduates: Low self-efficacy to self-regulate predicts higher levels of procrastination. *Contemporary educational psychology*, 33(4), 915-931.
25. Kurniadin, D., Rukanda, N., & Irmayanti, R. (2023). STUDI DESKRPTIF PROKRASTINASI AKADEMIK SISWA. *FOKUS (Kajian Bimbingan & Konseling dalam Pendidikan)*, 6(3), 162-168.
26. Lacson, A. J., Dimacali, C. A., Mora, D., Magos, M., & Salmorin, J. (2023). The Relationship Between Academic Burnout and Academic Procrastination Among Grade 12 Senior High School Students in a Private School. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 11(5), 1-1.
27. Lay, C. H. (1986). At last, my research article on procrastination. *Journal of research in personality*, 20(4), 474-495.
28. Lay, C. H., & Burns, P. (1991). Intentions and behavior in studying for an examination: The role of trait procrastination and its interaction with optimism. *Journal of Social Behavior and Personality*, 6(3), 605.
29. Lee, M., Lee, K. J., Lee, S. M., & Cho, S. (2020). From emotional exhaustion to cynicism in academic burnout among Korean high school students: Focusing on the mediation effects of hatred of academic work. *Stress and Health*, 36(3), 376-383.
30. Logenio, M. T. M., Godin, J. L., Paguio, A., Germar, R. A., Dablo, J. C., & Francisco, M. A. (2023). Procrastination and Academic Burnout Among Grade 12 Students in a Public School: A Correlational Study. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 11(6), 601-608.
31. Madigan, D. J., & Curran, T. (2021). Does burnout affect academic achievement? A meta-analysis of over 100,000 students. *Educational Psychology Review*, 33, 387-405.
32. Maloloy-on, E., Aquino, A. S., Marcelino, M. M., Mateo, M., Plaza, C. A., Endrina, S., & Tus, J. (2023). Procrastination and Its Relationship to the Academic Burnout of First-Year College Students in a State University.
33. Maslach, C., & Leiter, M. P. (1999). Burnout and engagement in the workplace: A contextual analysis. *Advances in motivation and achievement*, 11, 275-302.
34. Maslach, C., & Leiter, M. P. (2016). Burnout. In *Stress: Concepts, cognition, emotion, and behavior* (pp. 351-357). Academic Press.
35. Maslach, C., Schaufeli, W. B., & Leiter, M. P. (2001). Job burnout. *Annual review of psychology*, 52(1), 397-422.
36. Monteroso Jr, C., Hugo, A., & Bacatan, J. (2023). Total Quality Management Practices, Managerial Capabilities of School Administrators and Performance of Public Junior High School Teachers. *Cognizance Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 3(12), 221-337.
37. Morales, J. B., Llanes, W. L. L., Cabaluna, J. M. M., Cordero Jr, R. D., & Bacatan, J. R. Analyzing the Relationship Between the Sense of Efficacy and Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge of Teachers. *Indonesian Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 4(1), 99-108.
38. Noor, S., Tajik, O., & Golzar, J. (2022). Simple random sampling. *International Journal of Education & Language Studies*, 1(2), 78-82.
39. Norez, D. (2017). Academic burnout in college students: The impact of personality characteristics and academic term on burnout.
40. Olson, N., Oberhoffer-Fritz, R., Reiner, B., & Schulz, T. (2023). Study related factors associated with study engagement and student burnout among German university students. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 11, 1168264.
41. Özhan, M. B., & Yüksel, G. (2021). The effect of school burnout on academic achievement and well-being in high school students: A holistic model proposal. *International Journal of Contemporary Educational Research*, 8(1), 145-162.
42. Pintrich, P. R., & De Groot, E. V. (1990). Motivational and self-regulated learning components of classroom academic performance. *Journal of educational psychology*, 82(1), 33.
43. Purnomo, A. W. A., Wibowo, A. E., Kurniawan, K., & Setyorini, S. (2020). The relationship between smartphone addiction, academic burnout and academic procrastination among university students during online learning. *Psikopedagogia Jurnal Bimbingan Dan Konseling*, 9(2), 81-86.
44. Qu, R., Ding, N., Li, H., Song, X., Cong, Z., Cai, R., ... & Wen, D. (2022). The mediating role of general academic emotions in burnout and procrastination among Chinese medical undergraduates during the COVID-19 pandemic: A cross-sectional study. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, 1011801.
45. Ramzi, F., & Saed, O. (2019). The roles of self-regulation and self-control in procrastination. *Psychol Behav Sci Int J*, 13(3), 555863.

46. Rosales-Ricardo, Y., & Ferreira, J. P. (2022). Effects of physical exercise on Burnout syndrome in university students. *MEDICC review*, 24, 36-39.
47. Ross, S. M. (2020). Introduction to probability and statistics for engineers and scientists. Academic press.
48. Ruy, B. T., Barbosa, A. C. M., Neto, P. P. M. F., Teixeira, V. D. S. M., Santos, M. C. S., Zuim, N. L., ... & de Abreu, J. V. (2023). Burnout syndrome in medicine students: an integrative literature review. *Seven Editoria*, 1882-1892.
49. Salmela-Aro, K., Kiuru, N., Leskinen, E., & Nurmi, J. E. (2009). School burnout inventory (SBI) reliability and validity. *European journal of psychological assessment*, 25(1), 48-57.
50. Saplavaska, J., & Jerkunkova, A. (2018, May). Academic procrastination and anxiety among students. In *17th International Scientific Conference Engineering for Rural Development* (pp. 23-25).
51. Sari, P., Kholidin, F. I., & Edmawati, M. D. (2020). Tingkat kejenuhan belajar siswa sekolah menengah pertama di kota bandar lampung. *Journal of Guidance and Counseling Inspiration (JGCI)*, 1(1), 45-52.
52. Schaufeli, W. B., Bakker, A. B., Van der Heijden, F. M., & Prins, J. T. (2009). Workaholism, burnout and well-being among junior doctors: The mediating role of role conflict. *Work & Stress*, 23(2), 155-172.
53. Steel, P. (2007). The nature of procrastination: a meta-analytic and theoretical review of quintessential self-regulatory failure. *Psychological bulletin*, 133(1), 65.
54. Tuckman, B. W. (1991). The development and concurrent validity of the procrastination scale. *Educational and psychological measurement*, 51(2), 473-480.
55. van Eerde, W., & Klingsieck, K. B. (2018). Overcoming procrastination? A meta-analysis of intervention studies. *Educational Research Review*, 25, 73-85.
56. Wang, Y., Gao, H., Liu, J., & Fan, X. L. (2021). Academic procrastination in college students: The role of self-leadership. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 178, 110866.
57. Wiwatowska, E., Pietruch, M., Katafoni, P., & Michałowski, J. M. (2023). "I can't focus now, I will study tomorrow"- The link between academic procrastination and resistance to distraction. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 107, 102364.
58. Xu, S. (2021). Academic procrastination of adolescents: A brief review of the literature. *online learning*, 21(39), 79.
59. Xu, J., & Ba, Y. (2022). Coping with students' stress and burnout: learners' ambiguity of tolerance. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 842113.
60. Yıldırım, A. & Şimşek, H. (2006). *Sosyal bilimlerde nitel araştırma yöntemleri* (6. bs.). Ankara: Seçkin
61. Zhou, M., Ye, B., Mynbayeva, A., Yong, L., & Assilbek, N. (2024). A cross-cultural comparison of academic burnout among Chinese and Kazakhstani secondary students. *Current Psychology*, 1-13.
62. Zimmerman, B. J. (2012). Goal setting: A key proactive source of academic self-regulation. In *Motivation and self-regulated learning* (pp. 267-295). Routledge.